

INTERNATIONAL TERMS IN ROMANIAN

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Abstract: *This article deals with international terms in the Romanian language, which were borrowed tale quale from other languages over the last 30 years. Moreover, these terms, designating certain new realities, are introduced, as such, in multiple languages simultaneously, in part due to the globalisation process that the society is undergoing and which results in the possibility of having a uniform understanding of the realities of all kinds, which, in turn, result naturally and immediately in a conceptual and linguistic homogenisation.*

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In the entire civilised world, there's a rapidly occurring lexical renewal, due to information technology, that promotes rapid communication and, more importantly, to the access of the public to information, mainly technical and scientific in nature. Thus, the possibility to have a uniform understanding of realities of all kinds is a result of the globalisation process experienced by our society, in general, which in its turn results, naturally and immediately, in a conceptual and linguistic homogenisation.

Therefore, some terms/terminological phrases, designating certain new realities, enter as such multiple languages simultaneously, which gives them the status of *international terms*.

Romanian, as a language that is very receptive to news in the financial, technical, social, scientific, and cultural fields, possesses the adequate means for such a linguistic renewal, adopting, in various ways, these international terms.

International terms can be grouped according to the fields to which they belong, as follows:

- arts: *a fresco, artnapping, body-painting, papier collé, papier mâché*, etc.;
- cinema: *blimp, blockbuster, box-office*, etc.;
- beauty: *anti-aging, beauty center, beauty trend, blush, paraben*, etc.;
- cuisine: *al dente, bacon, bisque, blender, bloody mary, bouquet garni, brie, broccoli, café-frappé, camembert, cannelloni, capélli d'ángelo, carambola, catering, cava, chili, chips, chorizo, churro, croque-monsieur, enchilada, fast-food, gazpacho, granadilla, hamburger, hot-dog, junk food, maracuja, mimolette, mixed-grill, mozzarella, paella, piña colada, quinoa, raclette, rambol, rambutan, sangria, tagliatelle, tapas, tortilla*, etc.;
- dancing: *breakdance, flamenco, kizomba, rap, rapper*, etc.;
- economics: *account executive, account manager, accounting manager, agreement, assistant manager, banner, barter, beach-bar, boom, brand, buy back*, etc.;

- finance: *banking, e-banking, internet banking, m-banking, mobile banking, pibor*, etc.;
- IT: *adserver, adservering, adware, antispyware, backdoor, background, backspace, backup, basic, blueray, browser, buffer, bug, byte, hard, multiprocessor, multitasking, networking, OCR, off-line, on-board, overclocking, soft*, etc.;
- mass-media: *advertiser, advertising, advertorial, airplay, art director, blow-in card, board, booklet, broadcasting, media planning, new media, outdoor*, etc.
- medicine: *acupunctură, acvafobie, adenom, ADHD, adictologie, ADN, adrenalină, borderline, breakdown, breaking news, bypass*, etc.;
- music: *after-beat, background, backing-vocalist, backing-vocals, backstage, beat, big band, block chords, maxi-single*, etc.;
- dog breeds: *chow-chow, collie, husky, rottweiler*, etc.;
- sports: *backhand, badminton, baseball, biker, bodyboarding, bodybuilding, bouldering, bowling, snowboard, taekwondo*, etc.;
- tourism: *all inclusive, backpacking, bed&breakfast, tour-operator*, etc.

General terms: AA (< Alcoholics Anonymous), ABS, AC, *accelerator, acces, acknowledgement, acquis-ul comunitar, acvacultură, add, adidas, adviser, after-hours, after-party, after-school, after-shave, all season, army, baby-doll, baby-sitter, baby-sitting, backgammon, big bang, big brother, black-out, blind date, blog, blogger, bluetooth, body, bodyguard, book, bookmark, boss, brainstorming, bumper, burqa, catwalk, CD, CD player, CD writer, CD-rom, CD-RW, hard, iaido, ikebana, piñata, mouse pad, notebook, prêt-à-porter, site*, etc.

Currently, the main source of lexical and semantic enrichment is the English language. It should be noted, however, that French which, in its turn, has shown openness towards the English influence in the last decades (see Le Petit Robert 2011, GRLF, 2011 edition) has not stopped providing new words and meanings, especially for the social and cultural fields.

We note, for example, that the main source languages in the field of gastronomy are especially: French (*bisque, bouquet garni, brie, café-frappé, camembert, cava, croque-monsieur, mimolette, raclette, rambol, rambutan* etc.); English (*bacon, blender, bloody mary, fast-food, junk food, hamburger, hot-dog* etc.); Italian (*al dente, cannelloni, capelli d'angelo, tagliatelle* etc.); Spanish (*cava, chili, chorizo, churro, enchilada, gazpacho, granadilla, multi-touch, must have, myspace, paella, piña colada, quinoa, sangria, tapas, tortilla*, etc.).

A special case is that of words designating realities from the Romanian cuisine, which have been introduced, as such, in other languages, for example some lexicographical works contain, in French, the word *mămăligă* "purée de maïs consommée avec un plat ou en galette" (GRLF 2014, s.v. *mamaliga*).

Likewise, the international terms that have entered the Romanian language via English and/or French, and not directly via their source language: *aikido* < Fr. *aikido* (Japanese word); *burqa* < Fr. *burqa, burka* (Arabic

word); *ikebana* < Fr., Eng. *ikebana* (Japanese word), *haşış* < Eng. *hashishi*, Fr. *haschisch* (Arabic word); *judo* < Fr., Eng. *judo* (Japanese word); *káki* < Eng., Fr. *kaki* (< Japanese word); *noni* < Eng. *noni* (< Tahitian word); *sálak* < Eng. *salak* (< Indonesian word), *sarong* < Fr. *sarong* (< Malaysian word), *saunã* < Eng., Fr. *sauna* (< Finnish word); *tae-bo* < Eng. *tae-bo* (< Korean word), *tahíni* < Eng. *tahini* (< Greek, Arabic word); *tantra* < Fr. *tantra* (< Sanskrit word); *tofu* < Eng., Fr. *tofu* (< Japanese word); *tsunami* < Fr., Eng. *tsunami* (< Japanese word); *wasabi* < Eng., Fr. *wasabi* (< Japanese word); *wok* < Eng., Fr. *wok* (< Chinese word); *zulu* < Eng. *zulu* (< Zulu word) etc.

Many international terms or very new words will, of course, find their own place in Romanian adding precision, accuracy, and flexibility. But the newest layer of neologisms which have just entered Romanian also contains many barbarisms, words which were introduced in the language without being necessary, especially from English. These Anglicisms will disappear, of course, over time just like French loan words at the beginning of the last century through a natural settling process. But until then, they are widely used, especially by Anglophiles; the rest of the Romanian speakers don't know their meaning and often have difficulties understanding messages, in particular from the mass-media¹.

The international nature of some of the neologisms is easy to note in the Romanian language dictionaries that we have analysed, as they often use a choice of multiple etymologies (see some examples above).

Many words that have been adopted *tale quale* from the languages with which Romanian speakers come into contact will acquire, in time, specific Romanian forms and will be integrated into the Romanian vocabulary. There are quite a few words that are likely to be abandoned or replaced with others, which are more suited to the Romanian language system.

In Romanian, many neologisms, in general, and international terms, in particular, have been adopted in different ways, allowing for the following sub-categorisation:

a) new loan-words from foreign languages, particularly English and French, some of them adapted, albeit only partially, to the morphological and phonetic system of the Romanian language: *adict*, *adidas*, *adviser*, *airbag*, *antiperspirant*, *audit*, *background*, *banner*, *bax*, *bestseller*, *betablocant*, *bip*, *bit*, *blazer*, *blister*, *blog*, *blogger*, *blura*, *bodyguard*, *brand*, *branding*, *briefing*, *broker*, *brokeraj*, *buffer*, *bug*, *bumper*, *business*, *card*, *cart*, *catering*, *chart*, *check-in*, *chips*, *cip*, *climatizor*, *climatronic*, *clip*, *clona*, *clonã*, *computer*, *comunitar*, *consumism*, *crawl*, *criogenie*, *criza*, *croissant*, *curricular*, *cutter*, *cybercultură*, *deadline*, *dealer*, *dealership*, *decomuniza*, *leasing*, *mop*, *mouse*, *multimedia*, *quarc*, *pacemaker*, *racket*, *rating*, *reloca*, *remake*, *repondent*, *respondent*, *ringtone*, *scoring*, *screening*, *scroll*, *shooting*, *sponsor*, *spot*, *staf*, *star*, *stent*, *(memory-)stick*, *sticks*, *stimulator (cardiac)*, *stres*, *stresa*, *stripper*, *subcontract*, *summit*, *supermarket*, *suspans*, *sustenabil*,

tabloid, tabuiza, taliban, talk-show, target, targeta, teflon, teleconferință, teleprompter, teleshopping, temporiza, termoizola, termoizolant, tester, thriller, tomograf, toner, topic, top-model, trade-center, trademark, trend, troler, tsunami, tuna (“decorate”), *update, update, upgrada, upload, uploada, xerocopia, xerox, xeroxa, yahoo, zip, zoom* etc.);

b) new loan-words from foreign languages, particularly English and French, non-adapted and used as such: *acquis (comunitar), adserving, adware, after-shave, al dente, all inclusive, anti-aging, army, baby-sitter, beauty center, big brother, brain-drain, burnout, buy back, challenge, checkout, check-up, checkpoint, cloning, comics, comeback, networking, new-wave, playstation, pole-position, pop-art, pop-corn, real-time, reality-show, roaming, science-fiction, scoring, scratch, shopping, sign-in, sign-out, taekwando, tagliatelle, ticketing, tiramisu, undo* etc.;

Many frequently used abbreviations appear in current Romanian, and some are borrowed *tale quale* from various sources: *CD, CD R, CD ROM, CPU, DVD, nick, RAM, rasta, SMS, www* etc.

Alpha-numeric abbreviations are also becoming a familiar feature in the current language: *4 x 4, 3D, 2.1, 4G* etc.

It may seem incredible, but some neologisms (in the category of barbarisms) are frequently used by the current speakers, and they sometimes exceed 100,000 occurrences. Thus, in Romanian and in French we have seen, on the Internet, situations like the ones that follow²:

- *account manager* (1,080,000 in Romanian, 2,307,000 in French);
- *advertising* (8,410,000 in Romanian, 4,570,000 in French);
- *advisor* (194,000 in Romanian, 833,000 in French)'
- *after school* (747,000 in Romanian, 446,000 in French), etc., to mention just a few.

This forces us to include such words in the series of recent neologisms (although many of these words are ephemeral), that the lexicographer who prepares certain dictionaries feels compelled to describe and define, to present in-context usage patterns, to establish their etymology, the areas of use, grammatical rules, etc.

As for the lexicographic treatment of these lexical elements, there is lately, both for Romanian dictionaries and for dictionaries published in other languages (in French, for example) a general tendency to introduce very recent neologisms into use. For Romanian, the volumes of the DLR that were published in recent decades included new words (few in numbers, truth be told) with a short life or lexical rarities: *dan* „degree awarded to martial arts masters”³, *dance* „electronic music genre”, *dao* „principle of Chinese philosophy”, *dealer, debirocratiza, debriefing* etc. Although they are more receptive to news, the general DEX or NDU dictionaries don't have many entries that consist of current vocabulary either.

In Romanian, just as in French, we notice the presence of the dictionaries that only cover neologisms. Romanian has an entire series of dictionaries:

DN, NDN (and subsequent editions), DCR³ (and the first two editions), DEN, DCSR, etc.⁴.

For comparison purposes, in the case of French, the proposals of the 2014 edition of Le Petit Larousse illustré are interesting, mentioned as point of interest (words like: *flaschcode*, *nanobiologie*, *biomimétisme*, *zumba*, *googliser*, *nomopobe*, *speed dating*, *démondialisation*, *slopestyle*, *art-thérapie*, *voxographie*, etc.⁵) or the proposals of the PRob dictionary, the 2014 edition (“living French, current words and phrases: *astroparticule*, *biothèque*, *caméo*, *clivant*, *coltan*, *dim sum*, *fadette*, *itinérance*, *locavore*, *microbiote*, *modeux*, *street art*, *transgénérationnel*, etc.”⁶).

The lexicographic treatment of recent neologisms (the category that includes international terms) has the following characteristics:

- an extremely reserved attitude in the thesaurus category of dictionaries for Romanian (DLR) and for French (TLFi);
- a rather served attitude in the general category of dictionaries for Romanian (such as DEX, NDU, DEXI) and for French (PRob, GRLF, GLLF);
- a very open attitude, in dictionaries dedicated to neologisms, both for Romanian (NDN, DCSR, DCR³) and French.

At the same time, the Romanian or French speakers use neologisms frequently, despite the strong recommendations made by the special commissions for the French language, for instance.

However, it should be noted that the policy on the neologic phenomenon is far stricter in France, compared to Romania.

Conclusion

The situation of the international terms - both in Romanian and in other languages - is an interesting one, allowing for in-depth research concerning the fields in which their presence is noticed, the adaptation to the source language, the direct or indirect origin etc.

Notes

¹Few recent neologisms have been used in literary fiction, which makes a first – and sometimes final – selection. For now, they are present in the media – in print or broadcast media; special terms (technical, scientific, etc.) have already been included in textbooks and treaties.

²Information was obtained at the beginning of 2014, using the advanced search feature of Google search, only for texts written in Romanian, for Romania, on the one hand, and in French, for France, on the other.

³Please note that, in such cases, the authors of the DLR have introduced an innovation concerning etymology: – Japanese word. As per Fr. *dan*. The direct source ranks second [!]. Similarly, *dao* – Chinese word. As per Fr. *dao*.

⁴See Pamfil *et alii*, 2013; <http://www.editions-larousse.fr/>.

⁵See <http://www.lerobert.com/dictionnaires-generalistes/dictionnaire-le-petit-robert-2014.html>.

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